

Strategic Multi-Factor Root Cause Analysis for Lead Time Optimization in Jewellery Manufacturing

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ABSTRACT: One of the strengths that company need to have been the ability to release new models faster than competitors. It will give the opportunity for the company to capture the market share. However, company need to have a quick mass producing for the new models after prototype released to the market. Slow mass producing will open the window for the competitor to imitate the prototype and give the chance for them to capture all the markets if they have quicker mass-producing time. This issue happens in jewellery companies in Indonesia, one of the companies is XYZ Company. Prototype models from XYZ company are widely imitated by competitors who have faster production time. To overcome this issue, company need to analyse the root cause of slow mass production process in the company. Based on this analysis, recommendations can be given to the company and applied to accelerate the production process so the company will not lose the market anymore. The root cause analysis was conducted by using a fishbone diagram with a case study in XYZ company. Through the analysis, it can be seen that the root cause of the slow production time is due to lack of human resources that involved in production. Based on this finding, series of measures such as hiring additional employees and implementing the overtime hours for the employee can be applied to speed up the production time and even increase the capacity.

KEYWORDS: Lead Time, Root Cause Analysis, Fishbone Diagram, Jewelry Manufacturing, Production Strategy

I. INTRODUCTION

In jewellery industry, competition between companies is not sit only in price, it's in model. Model design is a primary factor that considered by the customers whenever they want to purchase jewellery. In other side, price of gold jewellery is very influenced by the international pricing standard, hence price difference between companies isn't significant. Therefore, differentiation in design and model is the key competitive factor [1].

Consumers, particularly Millennials and Generation Z, prioritize jewellery models that align with their preferences, making an understanding of aesthetics and design functionality highly influential in their purchasing decisions [2]. Millennials and Generation Z, which currently dominate the jewellery market, have unique preferences that differ from previous generations in terms of style and design [3]. Research shows that they are more attracted to jewellery that reflects personal identity and innovative design, requiring jewellery companies to offer a wide variety of models that appeal to different consumer segments [4].

In this context, companies need to implement design innovation and leverage technologies such as 3D printing and digital marketing to attract interest and meet consumer expectations [5]. With the large number of players in the jewellery industry, an effective strategy is to build brand loyalty through a deep understanding of consumer behaviour and market orientation [6]. Creating a positive customer experience through appealing design aesthetics and high product quality can enhance purchase intention and brand loyalty [7]. Therefore, jewellery businesses are expected to develop product lines that cater to the needs of various groups, especially the younger generation who are constantly seeking something new and unique [8].

II. BUSINESS ISSUE

XYZ Company, one of the jewelry companies in Indonesia, faces significant challenges due to its slow production process. In an effort to keep up with dynamic market demands, XYZ Company is committed to releasing new models every month. However, the production timeline—taking 2 to 3 months after the preorder system is opened—makes the company vulnerable to competition. In response, competitors are able to replicate the released models in a much shorter time, typically only 1 month after the prototype is introduced online via social media and marketplaces.

To address this problem, A systematic root cause analysis technique, such as the fishbone diagram, is highly relevant for evaluating the reasons behind the production delays at XYZ Company. The fishbone diagram is useful for identifying cause-and-effect relationships, where the fish's head represents the main problem, and the bones represent categories of contributing factors [9]. This analysis can guide the company toward precise and strategic improvements, enabling faster production without compromising quality.

Various factors can cause bottlenecks in the jewelry production process, such as material constraints, production methods, and human resource capacity. In the jewelry industry, which increasingly utilizes modern technologies like 3D printing, production flexibility can be maximized to meet the demand for new models quickly and efficiently [10]. Specifically, direct metal laser sintering technology enhances efficiency by enabling the creation of complex and unique designs in a shorter time [11].

By integrating the correct analytical techniques and modern technology into the production process, the company will have a chance to reduce the time required to respond to the market demand as well as continuing to make innovation in design and model. Critical things that need to be done by XYZ company to maintain its position in the market are improving production efficiency and adapting to the changes of consumer preferences.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Fishbone Diagram

Fishbone or Ishikawa diagram is a cause-effect diagram that prominently used to visualize a quality of management systematically by identify, categorize and analyse all the root cause of the specific problem. Introduced in 1960s by Kaoru Ishikawa, this diagram resembles a fish skeleton, where head symbolize the main problem and the bone represent various categories of potential root cause such as People, Methods, Machines, Materials, Environment and Measurement [12].

1. **Manpower:** This category represents the root cause factor that related to the personnel, including skills, attitude, motivation, training and communication. Problems in this category may come from inadequate or insufficient training, worker fatigue, physical and psychological health and even ineffective communication among team members [13]. It is essential to address these human factors, as they significantly influence organizational performance and product quality [14]
2. **Machine:** This category related to the performance and reliability of equipment and technology that utilized in the processes. Problems may arise in this category due to malfunctioning equipment, insufficient maintenance or even outdated technologies [15]. Effective integration of technologies that align with the insights from fishbone analysis will enhance the production efficiency significantly [16].
3. **Method:** This category emphasizes the issue that may come from methodology and procedures applied during processes e.g. non-standardized procedures, insufficient documentation, etc. Implementing standardized methods and procedures is a crucial thing that can affecting the quality outcomes [17].
4. **Material:** This category related to raw materials, components and all inputs that required for production process. Some issues that typically come in this category are poor quality materials, improper storage and handling or even deviation in specifications itself [18]. Ensuring the reliability of supplier will prevent material-related issue, which can be identified by this fishbone diagram [15].
5. **Measurement:** This category related to the problem or issue that may come from the tools and methodologies of monitoring. Uncalibrated measuring equipment and inappropriate metrics are typical problems in this category [19]. Employing effective quality control and assurance is critical for this category to enhance the reliability and performance of process [20].
6. **Environment:** This category related to the external environmental factors such as temperature, humidity, ventilation system and working conditions that may impact to the production process. These issues may come from the unsuitable environmental conditions that could affect the production efficiency [21]. Understanding the environmental factor is an important thing that may lead the organization to become more resilient and efficient. Fishbone diagram can highlight several findings related to environmental factors [22].

In conclusion, fishbone diagram is an important tool that serves as a foundation to identifying and analysing all root cause of quality issue in several categories. Analysing the root cause by several category will ease the organization to develop target to improve quality and enhance the operational efficiency. Inherent risk in production process also can be mitigated [23]. As industries continue to evolve

in terms of technology and also changes in customers preferences, the analytical tool becomes a critical component that need to be applied to by organizations to keep the sustainability

B. Review of Relative Literature

Table I. Review of Relative Literature

Reference Journal	KPIs (Key Performance Indicators)	FB	JW	LT	HR	TC	CM	QT	SG
[20]	- Defect reduction rate - Productivity improvement (%) - Downtime reduction	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓
[14]	- AI accuracy in root cause identification - Maintenance cost reduction - Mean time to repair (MTTR)	✓	✓	✓		✓			✓
[10]	- Build success rate (%) - Post-processing time reduction		✓	✓		✓			✓
[11]	- Material waste reduction - Microstructure consistency - Production speed (units/hour)		✓	✓		✓			✓
[5]	- Energy efficiency - Design complexity score - Customization rate		✓			✓			✓
[4]	- Time-to-market reduction - Cost per unit reduction - Prototype iteration speed		✓			✓			✓
[24]	- Market responsiveness - IoT uptime (%) - Real-time data accuracy		✓	✓		✓			✓
[25]	- Predictive maintenance success - Training ROI (%) - Employee productivity growth			✓	✓				✓
[26]	- Skill gap reduction - HR program completion rate - Employee retention rate				✓				✓
[27]	- Leadership competency score - System uptime (%) - Anomaly detection speed		✓	✓		✓			✓
[15]	- Production cycle time reduction - Defect rate reduction - SOP compliance rate	✓	✓					✓	✓
[18]	- Audit pass rate - Defect recurrence rate - Root cause resolution time	✓	✓					✓	✓
[2]	- Cost of poor quality (COPQ) - Customer satisfaction score (CSAT) - Design adoption rate - Social media engagement						✓		✓

Reference Journal	KPIs (Key Performance Indicators)	FB	JW	LT	HR	TC	CM	QT	SG
[6]	- Brand loyalty index						✓		✓
	- Purchase intent growth								
	- Market share (%)								
[28]	- Innovation ROI (%)								✓
	- Carbon footprint reduction								
[29]	- Regulatory compliance rate								
	- Overtime utilization rate					✓			✓
	- Workforce adaptability score								
[21]	- Absenteeism reduction								
	- Workflow transparency score	✓	✓						✓
	- Error rate reduction								
[22]	- Communication efficiency								
	- Porosity defect rate	✓	✓					✓	✓
	- Inspection time reduction								
[16]	- Corrective action speed								
	- Process fidelity score	✓							✓
	- Error recurrence rate								
	- Training effectiveness								
[7]	- Price elasticity index						✓		✓
	- Sales volume growth								
	- Competitive pricing alignment								
[13]	- Defect reduction rate	✓		✓				✓	✓
	- Training completion %								
	- Process cycle time								
[9]	- Defect reduction rate	✓		✓				✓	✓
	- Training completion %								
	- Process cycle time								
[30]	- Defect reduction rate	✓						✓	✓
	- Training completion %								
	- Process cycle time								
[8]	- Defect reduction rate		✓				✓		✓
	- Training completion %								
	- Process cycle time								
[17]	- Defect reduction rate	✓		✓				✓	✓
	- Training completion %								
	- Process cycle time								
[19]	- Defect reduction rate	✓						✓	✓
	- Training completion %								
	- Process cycle time								
[23]	- Defect reduction rate	✓						✓	✓
	- Training completion %								
	- Process cycle time								

Reference Journal	KPIs (Key Performance Indicators)	FB	JW	LT	HR	TC	CM	QT	SG
[31]	- Defect reduction rate				✓				✓
	- Training completion %								
	- Process cycle time								
[32]	- Defect reduction rate				✓				✓
	- Training completion %								
	- Process cycle time								

Notes: FB: Fishbone / Root Cause; JW: Jewellery / Manufacturing; LG: Lag Time / Efficiency; HR: HR / Workforce; TC: Tech / 3D Printing; CM: Consumer / Market; QM: Quality / Measurement; SG: Strategy / Improvement

In this research, an analysis of the problem of production delays in the jewelry industry is conducted using a fishbone diagram (by taking a case study at XYZ Company). This research raises a new discussion where previous journals have not discussed the issue of production delays using a fishbone diagram. Journals such as [20] and [14] use fishbone analysis to identify root causes, but they do not discuss issues in the jewelry industry and have no relation to production delays. Meanwhile, journals such as [11] and [5] discuss production efficiency and the addition of the latest technology in production but do not evaluate the human resource aspect. On the other hand, journals such as [25] and [26] discuss HR, but do not specifically address process efficiency in the jewelry industry. This journal discusses all aspects comprehensively, starting from the human resource side, methods, and supporting strategies to improve company efficiency. In addition, there are rarely journals that discuss production optimization in the jewelry industry. This journal also discusses more applicable strategies, so they can be implemented in the production process, unlike the journals of [17] and [30] which only focus on analytical tools.

IV. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

A. Root Cause Analysis

The Fishbone diagram regarding the business issue at XYZ Company is shown in Figure IV.1. Based on the root cause analysis using the Fishbone diagram, several factors that may affect the production time are identified in terms of manpower, machine, method, material, measurement, and environment.

1) Manpower

Almost the entire production process at XYZ Company relies on manual labor from its workers. Therefore, it can be said that the production capacity of XYZ Company depends on the number of employees in the company. The current workforce capacity at XYZ Company is not aligned with the desired target. Currently, the production capacity can only manage to mass-produce the new model in 2–3 months, while the desired target is below 1 month. This lack of capacity is also evidenced by the accumulation of work in several rooms. In addition to the insufficient workforce capacity, the uneven skills or abilities of employees also affect production performance. Some employees can meet daily targets, while others are unproductive, thus hindering the production process. The shortage of workers is then addressed by using overtime. However, continuous use of overtime can lead to employee fatigue and ultimately reduce their performance.

2) Method

Almost all the work in the jewelry industry, including at XYZ Company, is done manually, relying on the skills of the workers. Currently, some processes are automated with machines, such as the slurry process, casting process, and plating process, which are assisted by machines. However, the remaining processes are still done manually. This manual work is an advantage, as it results in more original and authentic products, but it also causes the production process to be slower. In order for the production process to run well, an effective and efficient method is needed. Some procedures and working methods at XYZ Company are still less effective, because there is repeated work being done. XYZ Company needs to think about how to simplify the product working methods in the Company.

Figure 1: Fishbone Diagram for Business Issue in XYZ Company

3) *Machine*

The casting machine used by XYZ Company is quite old. It has been in use for almost 10 years, since the company was established. The age of the machine can lead to suboptimal performance and products that do not meet standards. However, the casting machine is currently still functioning optimally due to regular maintenance. In addition, several companies have developed the latest technologies such as direct casting or the newest 3D printing, which allow the production process to be faster and more effective. Meanwhile, XYZ Company still relies on old technology, namely manual casting processes and old 3D printing machines.

4) *Material*

Delays in raw materials such as gold and diamonds, or complementary components (such as wires and chains) used in making jewelry, can be one of the causes of production delays. Additionally, the readiness of work equipment also affects the production process. The production equipment used at XYZ Company mostly comes from overseas suppliers, so import regulations and the scheduling of orders and deliveries are factors that affect the availability of equipment and the smoothness of the production process.

5) *Measurement*

Planning and scheduling the mass production of new models needs to develop accurately and must be aligned with the company's production capacity. Proper planning and scheduling make the production process more effective and efficient. Other than that, lack of supervision over the performance of the employees and production can create problems in the production process. Unproductive and poorly monitored employees can reduce the company's productivity and disrupt production process significantly.

6) *Environment*

To control employee performance, it is very important also to make sure that communication between R&D and production teams is going well. R&D team must communicate and give clear procedures or techniques whenever new models are created. R&D team need to ensure the new model that they developed is feasible to be produced by the production team without any obstacles or difficulties either in terms of techniques or tools. Good communication between R&D and the production team will reduce potential issues during mass production of the models that may slow down production time.

B. Strategies Analysis for the Company

Based on the fishbone analysis above, XYZ Company needs to implement several strategies that can help make the production process more effective and efficient and reduce the production time of new models so that they can be launched faster and capture the market.

1) Manpower Strategies

The first and most important strategy that needs to be considered is from the manpower side. Manpower is the main resource that determines the production capacity at XYZ Company. Based on the analysis results at XYZ Company, the current workforce capacity has not been able to meet the required time targets. Therefore, there are several strategies that can be implemented to increase this workforce capacity.

The first strategy is to re-explore the existing capacity. Currently, employee performance in the company is still uneven. Some employees do not even meet the performance targets set by the company. One of the causes of this underperformance is the lack of employee competence. To overcome this, a retraining process is needed for employees who do not meet the existing performance targets. The training process includes hard skills training related to the jewelry-making process and soft skills training to help improve relationships and communication among employees. With good communication, skill equality can be improved, as employees can ask each other for help when facing difficulties in producing jewelry products [25], [31]

The second strategy is to use overtime hours. The use of overtime is the easiest and fastest step that can be taken, but it has an impact on employees. Excessive use of overtime can cause fatigue, which will eventually reduce employee performance. Therefore, further analysis is needed regarding the appropriate use of overtime, which has the least potential to cause employee fatigue [28], [29]

The third strategy is to increase the number of employees. To add more employees, further analysis is needed regarding the number of employees required and the appropriate process positions, so that the addition of employees can have a positive impact and maximize productivity [26], [32]

2) Method Strategies

The next strategy is a strategy from the method side. There are several production flows used to manufacture jewelry at XYZ Company. Some of the existing production flows are still less effective because they need to go through several rooms multiple times. Therefore, XYZ Company can re-evaluate the existing workflows and simplify the production flow to make it shorter and more effective [25], [31]

3) Machine Strategies

Some of the machines used at XYZ Company are old and outdated. Although they are still functional, some of the existing technologies are already obsolete. The next strategy that can be implemented is upgrading the existing machines with the latest technology. Of course, upgrading machines requires a considerable cost, so further planning is needed regarding which machines should be upgraded first, based on the condition of the least optimal machines [28], [29]

4) Material Strategies

The materials and tools used in jewelry production at XYZ Company mostly rely on overseas suppliers. This point is actually not a crucial factor causing delays in the production process because, so far, the required equipment and materials have always been available on time. However, preventive measures can be taken to avoid production delays by planning the ordering process for materials and equipment, as well as looking for backup local suppliers to serve as alternatives in case of issues with the current suppliers [26], [32]

5) Measurement Strategies

Planning and controlling at XYZ Company currently still rely on manual processes. One of the strategies that can be implemented to improve the planning and controlling process is by adopting a digital system. With digital planning and controlling system, the company can monitor its production process in real time and maintain the company's productivity [24], [27]

6) Strategi for Environment

One of the strategies that can be implemented to maintain the company's environment is by holding weekly meetings between the R&D team and the production team. By conducting regular meetings, it is expected that the relationship between the R&D team and the production team can be maintained and ensure the smooth production process of new models [10].

V. CONCLUSION

The competition in jewelry design within the jewelry industry is the main competition that determines whether a company can dominate the market or not. Therefore, jewelry companies need to continuously develop new models to attract consumer interest. To keep up with this, the company's ability to mass-produce these new models is also crucial. If the company is late in mass-producing the newly released products, there is a potential that the model will be copied by competitors and the company will lose the market for that model.

Based on research conducted at XYZ Company, the time required to mass-produce new products released by its R&D team is 2–3 months. Based on the fishbone analysis, it was found that there are still employees who are unproductive, which reduces the company's overall productivity. In addition, the number of employees is still insufficient to reduce the lag time to 1 month. Aside from the manpower aspect, it was also found that some machines are old and outdated, which also hinders the production process. From the method side, there are several workflows that are still inefficient.

Through the findings from fishbone analysis, several strategies are proposed, namely improving employee skills, increasing the number of workers and using overtime, simplifying production workflows, and replacing old machines with new machines and technologies. Through these strategies, it is expected that XYZ Company can mass-produce its new models faster than its competitors and maintain its market share.

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